

Supplementary Figure 4. General features of RNAseq analysis of *exo70Bs* adult plants. A) DiVenn diagram demonstrates similarities and differences in sets of DEGs determined for *B1* vs. WT, *B2* vs. WT and *B1xB2* vs. WT RNAseq comparisons. B) DiVenn diagrams demonstrate similarities and differences in sets of DEGs determined for chitosan treated WT and each of *exo70B* mutant lines upon chitosan treatment. C) Quality control of quantification of transcriptomic profiling of adult plants, mock (underlined with blue box) and chitosan treated (underlined with red box), from wild-type and genotypes *exo70B1* (*B1*), *exo70B2* (*B2*) and double mutant *exo70B1xB2* (*B1xB2*). Heatmap shows Jensen-Shannon divergence coefficients for individual sample comparisons. ermined for *B1* vs. WT, *B2* vs. WT and *B1xB2* vs. WT RNAseq comparisons. hannon divergence coefficients for individual sample comparisons.